

METHODOLOGY FOR WORKING WITH CHILDREN WITH LOW ASSIMILATION IN MUSIC CULTURE CLASSES OF SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Annotation: this article reflects on the technologies of teaching them to increase the activity of low-acquiring students in the lessons of the general secondary education school “music culture”.

Keywords: technological game, .music culture, performance, reader, musical activity, methodology.

Today, there is a great emphasis on education in our country, first of all, this focus is on the maturation of young people with our future as mature people. In music culture classes, it has a good effect to train students who have a vacancy to work independently. Independent activity makes a person elegant and present. This activity should develop in harmony with music education in schoolchildren of younger age. To do this, first of all, it is necessary to mentally prepare students for independent activities, instill in them confidence that they will be able to do something and perform this work qualitatively. The types of independent work in music culture lessons in schools of general secondary education should be, first of all, carefully thought out by the teacher, oriented towards the educational goal and continuous. In this, the possibility of each student should be taken into account, the age feature, interests should also not be overlooked. One of the conditions for the mental development of students is the complete “remembering” of assignments. Particular attention is paid to the fact that, having understood (imagined) the purpose of the work to be performed, they are able to determine its plan and choose the method of work, independently find the mistakes made and fix it.

It is useful to choose convenient methods for students to carry out tasks quickly, correctly, ask referential questions and recommend base words. In music culture lessons, it is natural that students have difficulties in qualitatively performing independent work. Because yet their imagination is bright, their vocabulary is not enough. Experiments show that children meditate faster when they work under the guidance of a teacher. In order for them not to get used to this, it is necessary to encourage them to think more independently of themselves. Recalling the events in the text in order to attract the attention of readers: Why did it happen? What should have been yours? by asking questions such as, approving of his opinion, “you'll find yourself thinking again”, “very good”, “very cool! it is useful to use stimulating words like”. If the child is satisfied with the independent work performed initially, his with increasing interests, he begins to carry out new-new types of work. Independent work results should always be repeated.¹

¹ Aranovsky M. Thinking, language, semantics // Problems of musical thinking / Comp. M.G.Aranovsky. - M.: Music, 1974.

It is necessary to instill in children, as far as possible, basic knowledge and skills in the classroom setting, to follow the norm when giving tasks to the House. It is good to master the lesson if children relax crisply after class, are more outdoors, spend time with action games, walks, sleep peacefully at night and come to the lessons of tomorrow in a good mood. Therefore, it should be easy to do homework, and, in principle, encourage children to observe, draw conclusions. It must be recognized that working with low-absorbing learners is a much more complex process. It can be effectively implemented as a result of the pedagogical skill of the teacher, the use of modern methods of conducting classes, individual work with a vacant mastering student.

In fact, we cannot lay the groundwork for young people to grow up to be holders of a highly qualified specialty, without enjoying the achievements of modern science and technology, and science in general. First of all, in the educational process, it is important to give students the right and purposeful knowledge.

In the course of teaching in each class, we come across students who have a low level of mastery of subjects. Working with these students requires a higher qualification from the teacher. In this process, it is necessary to ensure that the teacher's application of new methodologies increases the activity of low-acquiring students, thereby reaching the level of low-acquiring students among other peers. Only then is each elementary school teacher considered to have been able to properly organize his activities and carry out an individual process of work with each student.

It is important to protect students from tension and various psychological influences, to strengthen their knowledge through interesting games. An effective result is the teacher's use of games that encourage students to have elegance and agility and to express their opinion correctly and clearly. Identifying and working with low-acquiring students requires special lessons and responsibility from the teacher. Therefore, in order to engage in this category of children, first of all, it is necessary to conduct a solo conversation and determine which instrument or musical activity they are interested in. Methods such as keeping a special Journal and regular monitoring of children's appropriation, keeping a separate training book from the musical activities that are struggling for students are also effective. It is also important that positive changes in students are encouraged. In order to increase the activity of low-level learners in music culture classes, it is necessary to develop their ability to think independently as well as their speech. The teacher should also use many other methods when taking classes. The most important thing is that they work.

It is also important to organize music culture classes for students with a low level of mastery. Through this, not only the reading literacy of the student increases, but also the worldview expands. When teaching low-acquiring students to independent activities in music culture classes, the following should be followed:

- ❖ let each task to be given correspond to the capabilities of the reader and arouse interest;
- ❖ let the work be directed from easy to difficult, from simple to complex, understandable to the reader;²

² Podurovsky V.M., Suslova N.V. - Psychological correction of musical and pedagogical activity

- ❖ let the children awaken a sense of self-confidence in playing music, let them feel boldness in themselves when starting work;
- ❖ let the tasks performed independently be carried out one by one (we remind you that giving the same task for all readers is not an independent activity), of course, it is necessary to pay attention to the unoccupied student;
- ❖ separate space to replace the type of musical activities
- ❖ importance must be given;
- ❖ it is necessary to accustom empty adoptive children to fulfill this requirement, reminding them that everyone should start assignments at the same time and finish them at a certain time;
- ❖ assignments can be completed at different stages of the lesson;
- ❖ it is advisable to have continuity when working with a textbook, didactic materials.

In music culture classes, the use of advanced educational technologies is considered to be important for low-acquiring students. Because that student could not accept education for himself in traditional classes or in classes that were always held in a community. So with low-acquiring students, it is necessary to first apply all their methodologies individually, and then involve them in the process of collective methodologies and, as always, in education.

In music culture classes, low-mastering serves as a key factor in explaining the High Artistry in music to students, introducing them to the content and essence of musical works, nurturing their musical taste and developing their musical sense. In the development and formation of initial feelings and thoughts in low-acquiring students, of course, it is important to focus on the age and psychological-physiological characteristics of students, starting from the early stages of Education. In the first grade, the foundation of the teaching of music lessons is laid. Therefore, first of all, from the 1st grade, it is the main task to actively interest them in the lesson, be able to perceive music, develop their musical abilities and go to teach music literacy. To carry out these tasks, it is necessary that the teacher loves children, prepares well for the lesson, is able to correctly use all methods and principles, be a master of verbal skills, reveal the content of songs that are characteristic of children, beautiful, tender, adapted to the sound of children.³

The teacher should explain that certain feelings and thoughts are reflected in each musical Zamir, based on the life experiences of students, from the first lessons he will have a conversation about the non-spontaneity of musical works, about the fact that someone works and creates it with great creative work. To do this, "who makes the music?" , "Who performs?" , "Who listens?", he throws the question in the middle. When the character of the work to be studied is expressed figuratively, children understand it and clearly reveal its content. As you know, students of the 1st grade will have a different level of general understanding, knowledge about music. However, their impressions and musical experiences from everyday musical life remain close to each other. This is exactly what the teacher should take advantage of when uniting the classroom team.

³ Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). Use of innovative technologies in the educational process. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 713-718.

Based on the enrichment of impressions and experiences of low-acquiring children in connecting the content of the lesson with life, the level of knowledge about the simplest laws of music is expanded. The music culture lesson is planned on a program basis, using oral, practical, comparative methods of teaching music with visual weapons, involving low-mastering students in the lesson, performing dance elements, musical games, taking steps suitable for music, singing the bat with gentle expressiveness, is carried out on methodological requirements.

In conclusion, the use of modern pedagogical technologies in the organization of the process of working with low-acquiring students in the lessons of music culture of general Secondary Education shows its positive effect.

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